

KINETICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN CHLORINE UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE

BY M. V. RAMANAMURTI

The progressive development of the Joshi effect, Δi , during 'ageing' under discharge in freshly prepared chlorine-filled ozonisers, follows the equation for the 'first order' reactions. It is suggested that chemisorption, involving electron transference, is responsible for the formation of the excited boundary layer postulated in Joshi's theory of the phenomenon. The continued increase in the Joshi effect to a stationary maximum is attributed to a diminution with time of the 'work function' characteristic of the excited layer formed under discharge, and which is the chief seat of the Joshi effect.

The significance of the time variation of the electrical quantities for an analysis of the corresponding discharge reaction has been emphasized by Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; Deshmukh and Kane, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 23A, 247; Deo, *ibid.*, 1945, 21A, 76). The observation (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, Sec. III, p. 51) therefore, that the Joshi effect viz., an instantaneous and reversible diminution, Δi , of the discharge current i on irradiation of the discharge tube, is influenced markedly by ageing under a constant applied field, appeared to be of interest. It is found e.g., that a Joshi effect corresponding to 14 to 50% current diminution by exposure to but ordinary light, develops progressively under discharge (*vide infra*). Such continued increase of Δi under ageing at sensibly constant exciting conditions (*vide infra*) corresponds to the progress of a chemical change. Following Joshi's finding (*Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 175) that the course of a discharge reaction may be envisaged from the standpoint of the law of mass action, kinetic studies for the growth of the Joshi effect, Δi , are now made for the first time in this field.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general arrangement of the apparatus for the production of the electrical discharge in chlorine is shown in Fig. 1. A number of Siemens' type (glass) ozonisers were prepared by Prof. Joshi and filled with chlorine at gas pressures adjusted by him for the maximum effect Δi under short durations (not exceeding 30 sec. at a time) of exposure to the discharge. This restriction of time served to minimise the effect due to ageing now investigated. The results for the Joshi effect Δi refer to three from the above batch of ozonisers filled with the gas at 220 mm. pressure. They were excited under various applied fields and the discharge current i was observed at regular intervals by means of a reflection galvanometer actuated by a diode 83V (RCA), when the ozoniser was in the dark, (i_p) and when irradiated externally from an incandescent

TABLE I

T (mins.)	Ozoniser A				Ozoniser B				Ozoniser C							
	t _u	t _b	Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	k_1 , % Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	t _u	t _b	Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	k_2 , % Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	t _u	t _b	Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	k_3 , % Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	t _u	t _b	Δt , ($\times 10^3$),	k_4 , % Δt , ($\times 10^3$),
0	53	40	(40)	43.0 (43.0)	666	493	173 (174)	26.4 (26.4)	407	350	57 (60)	14.0 (14.0)				
5	50	41	(40.7)	43.8 (44.0)	-	-	1821	2.18 (28.5)	438	368	70 (70)	15.9 (15.6)				1.15
10	-	41.2	(45.4)	45.4	622	435	187 (190)	30.6 (30.0)	465	381	84 (80)	17.5 (17.2)				1.31
15	-	41.9	(45.9)	45.9	-	-	195	2.54 (32.3)	-	-	-	1.84 (18.5)				1.15
20	89	42	(42.5)	46.5 (46.7)	575	370	205 (200)	36.0 (35.0)	-	-	-	1.70 (19.9)				1.16
30	92	44	(43.5)	48.0 (48.0)	548	441	207 (207)	38.1 (38.1)	495	385	110 (110)	22.5 (22.4)				1.16
45	92	45		49.0	568	341	227	40.5	500	368	132 (130)	26.4 (26.0)				1.15

TABLE I (contd.)

T (mins.)	Ozonifer A					Ozoniser B					Ozoniser C							
	t_p	t_L	Δt	k_0 ($\times 10^3$)	$\% \Delta t$	k'_0 ($\times 10^3$)	t_b	t_L	Δt	k_0 ($\times 10^3$)	$\% \Delta t$	k'_0 ($\times 10^3$)	t_b	t_L	Δt	k_0 ($\times 10^3$)	$\% \Delta t$	k'_0 ($\times 10^3$)
60	82	42	40	49.5	49.5	581	337	244	41.9	41.9	575	365	140 (140)	167	28.0 (28.9)	1.19		
90	94	49	46	48.5	48.5	576	332	244	42.4	42.4	441	291	150		34.5			
120	91	45	46	49.5	49.5	506	276	230	45.5	45.5	430	264	166		38.5			
150	94	47	47	50.0	50.0	506	268	238	47.0	47.0	432	260	172		39.8			
180	96	49	47	49.0	49.0	504	270	234	47.5	47.5	429	248	181		42.0			
210	96	48	48	50.0	50.0	505	267	238	47.5	47.5	429	247	182		42.5			
240	96	48	48	50.0	50.0	509	269	240	47.5	47.5	437	250	187		42.8			
270	96	48	48	50.0	50.0	509	268	241	47.5	47.5	431	246	185		42.5			
300	96	48	48	50.0	50.0	509	268	241	47.5	47.5	431	246	185		42.5			
			(48)	(50.0)	(50.0)		(243)	(243)	(47.5)	(47.5)		(185)	(185)		(42.5)			

The quantities within the brackets were read off from the Δt -time and $\% \Delta t$ -time curves in Fig. 2, and used in calculating k and k' for early stages of 'ageing' under the discharge.

100 watt, 220 volt (glass) bulb, (i_0). From these data the net Joshi effect, $\Delta i = (i_0 - i_t)$ and its relative value $\% \Delta i = \frac{100 \cdot \Delta i}{i_0}$ were calculated. The results obtained in all cases were essentially similar. They have been sufficiently represented by one typical group of data given in Table I and in part in Fig. 2, corresponding to an exciting potential 2.4 kV of 50 cycles frequency at the room temperature (27°).

D I S C U S S I O N

The theory of the above effect Δi , as advanced by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, Part III, 1946, *Phys. Sec.*, *Abst. No. 26*; *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, **16**, 19) contemplates three stages, viz., (i) a boundary layer is formed on the container walls, derived in part, from adsorption of ions and excited molecules under the applied fields, when intense enough to break down the gas dielectrically, at the threshold potential V_m ; (ii) photo-electric emission occurs from this boundary layer under external irradiation; and (iii) these photo-electrons are captured by the excited neutral molecules to form slow moving negative ions which are responsible for the current decrease, Δi , as a space charge effect (Joshi, *loc. cit.*)

Work in these laboratories has shown that the boundary layer contemplated in (i) is fundamental not only to the Joshi effect but a number of other phenomena e.g., 'ageing' and the newly observed periodic effect in N_2O-H_2 and other reactions under electrical discharges. Since the stages (ii) and (iii) are instantaneous and fully reversible, it would follow that *ceteris paribus*, a time-variation in the magnitude of Δi under 'ageing' is determined practically entirely by the extent to which stage (i) occurs, and hence the curves, Δi , ($\% \Delta i$)—time, represent the course of the reaction occurring in stage (i). Significantly, the Joshi effect (Δi) and its relative value ($\% \Delta i$) in all the cases were found to increase progressively; they, however, became stationary after exposure of about five hours to discharge depending upon the operative conditions (*cf.* curves in Fig. 2). The difference of the final stationary value for Δi (or $\% \Delta i$) and the value at the commencement viz., Δi_0 (or $\% \Delta i_0$) measures the total net production of the change and corresponds to the initial concentration term 'a' in the familiar equations for the (chemical) reaction-velocities. Similarly, the difference of Δi_t (or $\% \Delta i_t$) at any time t and Δi_0 (or Δi_0) is a measure of 'x', the amount changed. The results given in Table I show that the values of Δi (or $\% \Delta i$), reckoned since the commencement of 'ageing' under discharge for each of the three ozonisers A, B and C, yield a sensibly constant value for the velocity coefficient 'k', when the equation for first order reactions is used. It may be mentioned that the values for Δi (and $\% \Delta i$) used in the calculation of the velocity coefficient, k , were read off from the smooth curves in Fig. 2 and are shown in parenthesis below the actually observed corresponding quantities in Table I. The above constancy in the unimolecular coefficient (k) also applied to the results (not shown) obtained with the ozonisers A, B and C at potentials other than the one to which Table I and Fig. 2 refer. This remark again applied to corresponding results (not shown) obtained with the other ozonizers, i.e., besides A, B and C. The data in Table I show that during the periods over which the velocity coefficients, k

FIG. 2

and k' , have been calculated, the current in dark, i_0 , and the same under light, i_L , do not show an identical time-variation; thus *e.g.*, with the ozonisers A and B both the above quantities show a progressive decrease with time; the ozoniser C, however, shows the opposite. The significant result that the time-variation in respect of both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ yields series of constant velocity coefficients suggests that the Joshi effect is more a characteristic of the boundary layer than of the conductivities in dark and under light.

In view of the above observation that Δi under ageing progresses according to the unimolecular law for chemical reactions, it is suggested that the type of adsorption involved in the formation of the boundary layer postulated by Joshi for stage (i) may be predominantly 'chemical' in nature. McBain ("The Sorption of Gases by Solids," Routledge, 1932) has pointed out that sorption of gases occurring on solids under normally "unfavourable" conditions *e.g.*, high temperatures, is due to energised molecules or atoms being attached to the solid surface with electron transference, which is observed markedly in the case of elements like chlorine, bromine and oxygen. It is found by James Taylor (*Nature*, 1928, 121, 708; *ibid.*, 1928, 122, 347) that a passage of electric discharge through a gas favours condensation *e.g.*, a large and progressive decrease, to a slight trace finally, of the hydrogen content (indicated spectrographically) in hydrogen-neon tubes was observed when the tubes were excited. His experiments on helium again has shown that the disappearance of the gas under discharge is not due to an accelerated diffusion through the pores of the glass

wall. He attributed this to sorption of the gas on the container walls. This he preferred to the concept of a purely physical adsorption. From the studies of the regular contraction of hydrogen under discharge, De Laplace (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, 187, 225) showed that it was not due to the formation of triatomic hydrogen. The experiments of Hill (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1912, 25, 35), Willows and George (*ibid.*, 1916, 28, 124) on sorption of gases in vacuum tubes under discharge also confirmed that it was a result of a chemical action. This boundary layer formed under discharge therefore is to be discriminated from physical adsorption attributed by Langmuir to the operation of van der Waals forces, which is determined by the pressure of the gas, the temperature and the mass of the adsorbent and occurs practically *instantaneously* and cannot therefore be fundamental to 'ageing' *i.e.*, the time development of the Joshi effect, Δi . Hence the other type, *viz.*, chemisorption associated with the molecules possessing high activation energy (and therefore particularly probable under a discharge reaction), formed with the aid of valency forces and characterised by a large heat of adsorption, should be fundamental for the formation of the boundary layer. This excited gas layer on the electrode walls therefore is a result of the molecules on the surface being activated due to the ionic bombardment under discharge at a fixed applied field and consequently undergoing a more stable condensation on the walls by means of distorted 'electron transference.'

The photoelectric emission from this layer is determined by the 'work function' which is much smaller than the corresponding ionisation potential in the gaseous condition. The production of Δi therefore, at frequencies too small for photo ionisation follows (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19). With continuous activation due to ionic bombardment under the discharge (*i.e.* during 'ageing' under the discharge) the work function should diminish and the relative Joshi effect increase correspondingly to a stationary maximum as observed.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY.

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